

Principals' Diversity Management as Predictors of Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated principals' diversity management as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by four research questions and four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised all the 8,189 teachers in 269 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to draw 819 teachers for the study. A researcher developed instruments titled "Diversity Management Scale (DMS)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded coefficient values of 0.79 for DMS and 0.82 for TJPQ respectively. The researchers together with three research assistants collected data for the study using the direct delivery method which yielded 98% return. Simple regression was used to answer research questions and hypotheses 1-3, while multiple regression was used to answer the research question and hypothesis 4. The findings of the study revealed among others gender, age and cultural diversity management strongly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found out gender, age and cultural diversity management significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education should modify the existing policies that prohibit gender discrimination and clearly communicate to all principals of secondary schools.

Keywords: Diversity, Management, Gender, Age, Cultural, Teachers, Job Performance, Schools

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Introduction

Workforce of many organizations is made up people who are mixed in terms of gender, age, educational, race and cultural background. The different characteristics and demographic variables of personnel create diversity in the workplace. Ajani (2023) described workplace diversity as how individuals in an organization differs by gender, ethnicity, age, physical abilities, lifestyles and religion. Work diversity is the attributes, lifestyles, values and belief system that distinguish individuals in an organization. Workplace diversity is defined by IHEMEJE, EZECHI, AJEFU and OLASEHINDE (2023), as the similarities and discrepancies in age, gender, race, religion, knowledge, academic qualifications and culture among employees in an organization. It is the duty of managers to strike a balance between work roles and unique identities, cultures and lifestyles of workforce. Every organization or institution can utilize the unique features of each worker to attain predetermined goals through diversity management.

Diversity management is the act of accommodating, respecting, valuing and utilizing the differences and similarities that exists among members of staff in an organization. When employees feel valued, respected, and included in activities of an organization, they are more likely to be motivated, committed, and satisfied with their work (Adubasim, & Ufomba, 2024). Diversity management is the process of ensuring inclusiveness and engaging non-discriminatory practices in the workplace. Iibi (2019) described diversity management as a combination of programmes, policies and activities that create an environment where employees' variances are valued and united into each part of the school's operations. The author added that diversity management is concerned with efforts of school administrators to ensure that all people are valued regardless of their differences. The notion of diversity management is to create comfortable and inclusive work environment for all members of staff irrespective of their varied background and characteristics. Atmaja and Dewi (2024) posited that the aim of diversity management in an organization is to create and maintain a positive work environment that appreciate the similarities and differences of individuals in the workplace. Nworie and Onyeizugbe (2024) noted that diversity management is concerned with cultivating and maintaining a conducive work environment that honours individuals' similarities and differences to enable all staff to realize their potential and enhance their contributions to the actualization of organization's strategic objectives and goals. Diversity management is the initiative, actions and programmes that provide equal working conditions and

opportunities for all members of staff in an organization. The crucial areas for diversity management include: gender, age, culture, job tenure and educational qualifications among others.

Gender diversity is the variations in the composition of male and female staff of an organization. According to Nworie and Onyeizugbe (2024), gender diversity management deals with the equal representation of men and women in different units and activities in a place of work. Gender diversity management is the provision of equal opportunities for male and female staff to get involved in the day-to-day activities and operations of an organization. Ekejiuba, Muritala, Maitala and Nwoye (2023) pointed out that gender diversity management is the impartial and just treatment of male and female employees. Furthermore, Ekejiuba asserted that it involves offering employment, pay, training or promotion equally to all prospective and existing male and female employees without discrimination and favouritism. Gender diversity can be effectively managed by administrators who ensure gender balance in the number of recruitment, persons in various committee and administrative positions. Ossai Oyibokure (2024) averred that it is the responsibility of school administrators to develop and implement policies that explicitly address gender equality and combat discrimination in schools. The authors added that this could include setting clear guidelines to avoid harassment and bullying, ensuring gender-balanced leadership positions and creating a safe space for open dialogue on gender issue. Gender diversity is managed through ensuring equal work roles and benefits for male and female staff in the same positions within educational institutions.

Age diversity is the age make-up of personnel within an organization. Turi, Khastoori, Sorooshian and Campbell (2022) maintained that age diversity is the ability of an organisation to accept different age groups. Continuing, Turi et al posited that many organisations are welcoming age diversity because they need skilled old employees with experience and young talent with an innovative mindset for new ventures better organisational performance. Obasi and Igbudu, (2021) noted that teachers who grew up and are employed in different times may have different perceptions of what the profession is all about, their expectations, values, mode of communication, content of curriculum and method of teaching delivery which make imperative for age diversity management. Age diversity management is the act of valuing and showing equal respect to the differences and similarities that exists among young and older personnel in an organization. Age diversity can be effectively managed by administrators who take into consideration the different needs, expectations and values of the various age groups in assigning tasks and rewarding their performance in secondary schools. Administrators can manage age diversity by pairing the old and young staff in discharging some duties in schools. Hamisu, Zakari, Ahmad and Olaniyi (2021) noted that having an age diverse environment produces and creates better working relationships

and enhances social cohesion for all. Elimination of age barriers in recruitment, placement and job description of staff into positions in educational institutions is one of the ways of managing age diversity.

Cultural diversity is the existence of people with different beliefs, customs, values and ways of life in an organization. Turi, Khastoori, Sorooshian and Campbell (2022) pointed out that cultural diversity is differences in religion, language, and ethnic backgrounds of people working in an organization. Turi et al added that employees from different cultural backgrounds working in the same organization have different lifestyles, beliefs, and skills that can improve strategic decisions and smooth functioning of daily activities in the workplace. Tran and Ngo (2020) asserted that cultural diversity management is structure in which customs, languages, norms and beliefs of all sundry of people in an organization or society are recognized and respected. Cultural diversity management is the equal acceptance and treatment and acceptance of people with different ways of life and belief system in an organization. Ndubuisi-Okolo, Ekwochi and Agbaji (2023) noted that employees all over the world find themselves in organizations with different cultural background, due to globalization. Continuing, the authors stressed that management at all levels must apply concerted effort to apply management strategies in ensuring that the environment they work accommodates all and sundry. Morris (2023) argued that cultural diversity is managed through removing barriers of biases, discrimination, and inequality in dealing with people from different ethnical backgrounds. Cultural diversity management enable members with different perspectives, values and experience to share ideas that open the door to innovation in educational institutions. Adubasim and Ufomba (2024) noted that when individuals with different cultural backgrounds, perspectives, and experiences come together, they bring a wider range of ideas and insights that can lead to more innovative problem-solving for improving their job performance in the workplace.

Teachers' job performance is the achievement and contributions of members of teaching staff to the success of learning institutions at the specific period. According to Arinze, Egboka and Nwosu (2024), teachers' job performance is the outcome of the day-to-day work carried out by academic staff in schools. Furthermore, Arinze et al posited that it is the result of effort made by teachers in using the available resources to achieve predetermined objectives. Teachers' job performance is the engagement of teaching staff in work activities to complete assigned tasks for attainment of set educational objectives. Teachers' job performance is defined by Nwokporo and Nwankwo (2024), as the result or outcome of the tasks executed by members of teaching staff in education institutions. Teachers' job performance could be high or low in educational institutions. A high job performance usually exceeds expectations in discharging official duties. On the

contrary, a low job performance of teachers is usually acting below expectations in discharging official duties. According to Ogwurumba and Ikediugwu (2024), teachers' job performance is concerned with all the activities carried out by the teacher to achieve desired effects on students. Continuing, Ogwurumba and Ikediugwu maintained that it involves the extent to which the teacher participates in overall running of the school in order to achieve expected school objectives and goals. Teachers' job performance is the degree in which members of teaching staff discharge their duties, engage in school functions and carry out tasks assigned to them in a given period to achieve predetermined goals in educational institutions.

The teachers' job performance could be assessed through their lesson preparation, instructional delivery, use of appropriate teaching materials, classroom management, coverage of scheme of work, engagement in continuous assessment of learners, participation in school functions, involvement in co-curricular activities, administering and marking of homework given to students, cleanliness of classroom and grading of students in tests and examinations and learning outcomes among others. Similarly, Ibezim (2024) asserted that the job performance of teachers could be assessed through the work activities such as lesson preparation, utilization of instructional resources, classroom organization, instructional delivery, conducting of examination and preparation of results among others.

The job performance of teachers in some aspects is below expectations in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Arinze et al (2024) noted that there is remarkable job performance of teachers as reflected in students' academic achievement but there are laxities in some areas in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Continuing, Arinze et al asserted that some teachers appear to be absent from school without fair reason, unavailable in classes to teach at the stipulated periods in the timetable which might lead to inability to and fail to cover their scheme of work. Some teachers appear to show up late to class, exhibit frequent absence from work, leave early before closing hour, fail to meet due dates for completion of scheme of work and underutilized some instructional materials in presenting their lesson. Some teachers tend to perform below expectations in managing classroom which could be responsible for noise-making and loitering of students during instructional period. Some teachers probably perform below expectations due to favouritism and discrimination practices in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Some principals tend to give preferential treatments to members of staff and students based on their gender, gender, physical ability and ethnicity in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Eziamaka, Nwakanma, and Onyilibe (2025) noted that delegation of tasks and allocation of resources and positions in the school by principals are not based on teacher's ability or specialization but their features, support and loyalty to them in public secondary schools in

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Anambra State. The authors added that these series of unfair practices may be the reason most teachers display poor performance to their duties in the school, as could be observed in their poor attitude to work, absenteeism, lack of dedication to teaching and carrying out assigned tasks. Ironkwe, Okechukwu, Obiekwe, Eziamaka and Mokwe (2025) noted that there are cases of discrimination or harassment, which has negatively impacted teachers' personal lives and pedagogical proficiency in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The authors added that inequitable practices in workload distribution and recognition seem to be common among the administrators in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Whenever, staff and students are discriminated based their gender, age, physical ability or ethnicity, they could become feel offended and this demoralize them from engaging in activities in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These problems prompted the investigation into diversity management as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate diversity management as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to investigate:

1. the predictive value of gender diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. the predictive value of age diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. the predictive value of cultural diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. the predictive value of diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of gender diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of age diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the predictive value of cultural diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
4. What is the predictive value of cultural diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

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Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. Gender diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Age diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Cultural diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. Diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised all the 8,189 teachers in 269 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to draw 819 teachers for the study. A researcher developed instruments titled "Diversity Management Scale (DMS)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. DMS contained 23 items spread in three clusters (A-C). Cluster A had nine items on gender diversity management, Cluster B had seven items on age diversity management and Cluster C had seven items on cultural diversity management. The second instrument titled TJPQ 25 items which measured teachers' job performance. The items of both instruments were placed on a 4-point rating of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded coefficient values of 0.79 for DMS and 0.82 for TJPQ respectively.

The researchers with the help of three research assistants adopted a direct approach for data collection. A total of 819 copies of instruments were distributed and 804 copies of questionnaires were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 98 percent return. Simple regression was used to answer research questions and hypotheses 1-3, while multiple regression was used to answer the research question and hypothesis 4. For decision on the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Alsagr (2021), as follows:

Predictive Values	Interpretations
0.00- 0.19	Weak

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0.20- 0.39	Fair
0.40- 0.69	Moderate
0.70- 0.89	Strong
0.90- 0.99	Very strong
1.00	Perfect

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less than significant value of 0.05 ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$), the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than, the significant value of 0.05 ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$) the null hypotheses was accepted. Result

Results

Research Question 1: What is the predictive value of gender diversity management on teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Gender Diversity Management as a Predictor of Teachers’ Job Performance in Secondary Schools

Model	n	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Gender Diversity Management	804	.867	.733	.731	.43655	Strong

The result in Table 1 reveals that the predictive value between gender diversity management and teachers’ job performance is 0.867 with a coefficient of determination of 0.733. This shows gender diversity management could account for 73.3% changes in teachers’ job performance. The regression coefficient r of 0.867 indicated that gender diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of age diversity management on teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Age Diversity Management as a Predictor of Teachers’ Job Performance in Secondary Schools

Model	n	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Age Diversity Management	804	.759	.624	.621	.44006	Strong

Table 2 reveals that the predictive value between age diversity management and teachers’ job performance is 0.759 with a coefficient of determination of 0.624. This shows age diversity management makes 62.4% contributions to teachers’ job performance. The regression coefficient

r of 0.759 indicated that age diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: What is the predictive value of cultural diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Cultural Diversity Management as a Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools

Model	n	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Cultural Diversity Management	804	.801	.717	.709	.50663	Strong

As shown in Table 3, the predictive value between cultural diversity management and teachers' job performance is 0.801 with a coefficient of determination of 0.717. This shows cultural diversity management could bring about 71.7% alterations in teachers' job performance. The regression coefficient r of 0.801 indicated that cultural diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 4: What is the predictive value of diversity management on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 4: The Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Diversity Management as a Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools

Model	n	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Diversity Management	804	.871	.785	.783	.35422	Strong

The result in Table 4 reveals that the predictive value between diversity management and teachers' job performance is 0.871 with a coefficient of determination of 0.785. This shows 78.5% changes in teachers' job performance could be explained by diversity management. The regression coefficient r of 0.871 indicated that diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One: Gender diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Gender Diversity Management as a Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	n	r	r ²	F	P-value	Remark
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Gender Diversity Management	804	.867	.733	454.116	.000	*S
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*Significant

Table 5 indicated that the predictive value between gender diversity management and teachers' job performance is 0.867, while the r^2 is 0.733. This shows 73.3% changes in teachers' job performance could be explained by gender diversity management. The $F(1/804) = 454.116$ and the p -value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, gender diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two: Age diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Age Diversity Management as a Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	n	r	r^2	F	P-value	Remark
Age Diversity Management	804	.759	.624	369.054	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 6, the predictive value between age diversity management and teachers' job performance is 0.759, while the r^2 is 0.624. This shows age diversity management could make 62.4% contributions to changes in teachers' job performance. The $F(1/804) = 369.054$ and the p -value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, age diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three: Cultural diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 7: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Cultural Diversity Management as a Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	n	R	r^2	F	P-value	Remark
Cultural Diversity Management	804	.801	.717	422.368	.000	*S

*Significant

Result in Table 7 indicated that the predictive value between cultural diversity management and teachers' job performance is 0.801, while the r^2 is 0.717. This shows cultural diversity management could bring about 71.7% changes in teachers' job performance. The $F(1/804)$

=422.368 and the p -value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, cultural diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Four: Diversity management is not a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 8: The Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis on Diversity Management as a Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	n	r	r ²	F	P-value	Remark
Diversity Management	804	.871	.785	435.256	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 8, the predictive value between diversity management and teachers' job performance is 0.871, while the r^2 is 0.785. This shows diversity management could make 62.4% contributions to changes in teachers' job performance. The $F (1/804) = 435.256$ and the p -value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that gender diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Antwia, Mensahb and Glover (2023) which showed that there was a strong correlation between gender diversity management and employee performance. This also supported the finding of Hamisu, Zakari, Ahmad and Olaniyi (2021) which revealed that there was a strong positive relationship between gender diversity management and employee performance. The possible explanation for this finding is that gender diversity create an atmosphere of equitable treatment, trust and mutual respect which promote a culture of collaboration and innovation that strongly contribute to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Gender diversity management ensures that male and female teachers are valued, respected and supported which perhaps explain the strong predictor of their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that gender diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in conformity with the finding of Antwia, Mensahb and Glover (2023) which showed that there was a significant correlation between gender diversity management and employee performance. This also in agreement with the finding of Hamisu, Zakari, Ahmad and Olaniyi (2021) which revealed that

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there was a significant relationship between gender diversity management and employee performance. Gender diversity management makes male and female teachers to feel heard and appreciated which account for significant predictor of their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The result of the study indicated that age diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Hamisu, Zakari, Ahmad and Olaniyi (2021) which showed that there was a strong positive significant relationship between age diversity management and employee performance. This is in consonance with the finding of Antwia, Mensahb and Glovera (2023) which revealed that age diversity management had a strong correlation with worker performance. This also affirmed the finding of Gowrishankar and Kanagaraj (2017) which indicated that there was a strong relationship between age diversity management and employees' performance. The finding could be explained by the fact that acceptance and management of teachers of different ages enable them to share their various skills and viewpoints that can strongly improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Age-diverse teachers offer valuable experiences which foster creative problem solving that improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Further result showed that age diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Antwia, Mensahb and Glovera (2023) which revealed that age diversity management had a significant correlation with worker performance. This also upheld the finding of Gowrishankar and Kanagaraj (2017) which indicated that there was a significant relationship between age diversity management and employees' job performance. Age diversity management enable older teachers to mentor their younger colleagues which can significantly broaden their skills and improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

It was discovered that cultural diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Ajani (2023) which indicated that cultural diversity had a strong positive relationship with job performance of employees. Cultural diversity management bring teachers with different customs, beliefs and ways of life to learn from each other which improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Cultural diversity management enables teachers to leverage their varied values and experiences to improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also revealed that cultural diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This supported the

finding of Ajani (2023) which indicated that cultural diversity had a significant relationship with job performance of employees. Cultural diversity management creates harmonious and more exciting work environment among teachers from different background and thereby significantly improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The result of the study indicated that diversity management is a strong predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Adubasim and Ufomba (2024) which showed that there was a strong relationship between workplace diversity management and performance of employees. The possible explanation for this finding is that diversity management provide equal opportunities for teachers to access resources and fringe benefits which motivate them to work hard to improve their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Diversity management allows teachers to tap form colleagues with different perspectives, expertise and experiences that can improve their job performance. Further result showed that diversity management is a significant predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This also supported the finding of Adubasim and Ufomba (2024) which showed that there was a significant relationship between workplace diversity management and performance of employees. Diversity management provides opportunity for teachers to adapt, learn and get fresh ideas of executing their duties for improving their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that diversity management is a strong and significant predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Fair and equitable treatment of teachers regardless of their gender, age and cultural identify could boost their morale in discharging their duties to bring about substantial improvement on their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministry of Education should modify the existing policies that prohibit gender discrimination and clearly communicate to all principals of secondary schools.
2. Principals should implement age inclusive management approaches to provide equal work activities to all staff in secondary schools.
3. Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission should organize annual seminar for principals to keep them abreast with skills and knowledge of managing cultural diversity of staff in secondary schools.

4. Ministry of Education should mandate principals to constitute diversity management committee to oversee that school activities and tasks are carried out without discrimination based on gender, age and culture.

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